

MECHANISMS OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF SCHOOL EDUCATION IN MULTIMEDIA MEDIA

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Abstract: Multimedia tools are today the only and most modern form of information presentation. This article discusses the problems and disadvantages of using multimedia tools in the educational process, as well as their effective management mechanisms and gives recommendations.

Key words: information technologies, multimedia tools, information systems, problems and shortcomings, opportunities, interactivity.

Introduction:

The experience of using multimedia tools in the national education process of Uzbekistan is being formed. Because it is also the need of the hour. In addition to the traditional opportunities that determine the basis of social development in our society, advancing information tools are factors such as people's ability, initiative, creative approach to work, intellectual activity, and independent improvement of their knowledge and skills. The process of creating information related to the storage, transmission, and reception of large amounts of information envisages the development of computer technologies in various fields of human activity.

Human thinking is becoming so advanced that the process of technicalization and computerization is boldly entering not only various fields of production, but also the fields of culture and education. The rapid development of computer technologies has brought the educational process to a new level. This created the need to enrich with new knowledge and skills to revise the content, methods and forms of education.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Today, the level of professionalism of specialists working in various fields of our society is determined by their mastery of computer technologies. This has become the need of the hour. In order to meet this demand, a sufficient base must be created in the process of training specialists, that is, in educational institutions.

Currently, educational institutions are working on urgent problems such as creating the scientific basis of new pedagogical technologies, classifying them, and determining their methodological importance. New pedagogical technologies mean computerization of education along with traditional and non-traditional methods. In this sense, the increasingly formed computer-information culture, information culture creates new relationships in the delivery and reception of information, creates a new type of thinking. In this, a person interacts with the information universe. The combination of telecommunications (telephone, television, radio) networks with computer networks forms a single global information space, multimedia. The most important part of this space is the Internet network, especially its hyper-media services (World Wide Web), hypermedia mail, video conferences.

Multimedia (meaning "multimedia") is a complex concept of modern information technology. Multimedia collects, stores, processes and transmits information using various forms of information (text, table, graphics, speech, animation, multiplication), video image, music. Multimedia "human computer" is a new, improved level of interactive (dialogic) communication, in which the user receives very wide and comprehensive information. Multimedia tools are used in areas such as entertainment, education and advertising. Education of elementary school students on the basis of multimedia tools is one of the current issues.

The use of multimedia tools in the educational process is of great importance from the pedagogical and psychological point of view. The material provided in it is mastered more deeply, the opportunity to save time is achieved, the received information is stored in one's memory for a long time, the participation of students of junior school age as passive learners is reduced, multimedia programs aimed at improving curiosity and cognitive activity are implemented, education art is included in the process. In other words, multimedia activates motivations such as emotional-aesthetic influence, goal-seeking, and research. It is known that the learner remembers only a quarter of the subject he heard for the first time, and only a third of the material he saw; if he sees and hears, he remembers fifty percent of the information. When using interactive multimedia technologies, this figure is 75%.

RESEARCH OUTCOME

The method of organizing the teaching process based on multimedia tools is fundamentally different from the traditional teaching method, and it is for primary school teachers and students:

- Presentation of educational material in the form of images;
- Differentiated and individual education;
- Evaluating the learning and mastering process, communicating with them;
- Self-control and correction in the process of mastering the educational material;
- Demonstrating the studied topics and observing their interrelation;
- Use of computer and information technologies such as animation, graphics, multiplication of sound in science subjects taught and mastered in primary classes;
- Formation of skills for mastering academic subjects in primary school students;
- Such as creating new conditions for students to do independent work and learn topics.

The work carried out in this regard is related to the improvement and introduction of multimedia capabilities of modern information technologies in the educational system, their purposeful use leads to an increase in the effectiveness of the educational process. In this process, the multimedia tool increases the mastery of these subjects by applying them to each subject studied in the primary school. Meyer's principles of multimedia effectiveness.

Teaching through multimedia programs helps to systematize the content components of educational material on a large scale, allows learners to freely choose and switch to complete or reduced options of education. The new form of educational tools not only creates new opportunities for communication and information transfer, but also creates new problems, solutions, new problems that have a special place in modern culture compared to traditional education and certain mass media. also creates opportunities for intersection points.

The focus of the experience and practice of pedagogy on the person-oriented model of education is largely connected with the development of philosophical views that emphasize the human being in the center of scientific views. Personalized education is education that:

- Focused on the learner and focused on him as the main value of the educational process;
- To manifest and form the personal qualities of the learner, to develop his thinking, to develop him as a creative, active and initiative person, to satisfy his learning and spiritual needs; help to create conditions aimed at developing their intelligence, communicative and social skills, self-improvement and self-improvement skills;
- aimed at meeting the needs of society for specialists who are able to adapt to new social conditions, acquire new specializations and acquire knowledge independently.
- The use of multimedia tools in education provides an opportunity to:
- ensuring humanization of education;
- increase the efficiency of the educational process;
- development of the learner's personal qualities (assimilation, thirst for knowledge, independent education, self-education, ability to improve oneself, creative abilities, applying the knowledge gained in practice ability, interest in learning, attitude to work);
- development of communicative and social skills of the learner;
- the possibilities of individualization and differentiation of open and distance education will be significantly expanded due to individual (individual) education of each person with the help of computer tools and information electronic educational resources;
- looking at the learner as an active learning subject, recognizing his value;
- taking into account the personal experience and individual characteristics of the learner;
- conducting independent educational activities, in which the learner studies and develops independently;
- formation of skills in the use of modern educational technologies that help students to adapt to the current rapidly changing social conditions in order to successfully perform their professional tasks.

The process of self-directed education with the help of multimedia tools requires the development and use of modern, multi-disciplinary, subject-oriented multimedia educational tools. They include extensive databases, educational knowledge bases, artificial intelligence systems, expert-tutoring systems, laboratory practices with the ability to create a mathematical model of the studied process and phenomena.

DISCUSSION

According to the possibilities of taking into account the individual characteristics of learners and helping to increase their interest (motivation), as well as according to the qualities of compatibility, interactivity, flexibility of various types of multimedia educational information, multimedia is useful and productive education.

Providing interactivity is one of the important achievements of digital multimedia compared to other means of presenting information. Interactivity refers to providing information relevant to the learner's needs. Interactivity allows you to control the presentation of information to a certain extent: learners can individually change the settings defined in the program, study the results, respond to the program's request about a specific desire of the user, set the speed of presentation of materials and the number of repetitions possible. But it is important to consider a number of aspects when using multimedia. Educational materials presented in multimedia should be easy to understand, provided with modern information and convenient tools.

In order to fully reveal all the possibilities of multimedia technologies and to use them effectively, students need the support of a potential (competent) teacher.

As with the use of textbooks, in the use of multimedia tools, the educational strategy is enriched with content only when the teacher is engaged not only in providing information, but also in helping, supporting and guiding the learning process possible. Presentations enriched with beautiful images or animations are usually more attractive than plain text and can complement the material being presented and provide the necessary emotional level. Multimedia tools can be used in harmony with different educational directions (styles) and can be used by people with different mental and age characteristics of learning and receiving knowledge: some learners directly and some like to learn and acquire knowledge by hearing and others by watching (video films). Interactive multimedia technologies provide non-traditional convenience to the learner with academic needs. In particular, it ensures the growth of phonological skills and reading skills in students with hearing impairment, as well as their visual acquisition of information. For those with speech and physical disabilities, it allows them to use the tools based on their individual needs. Multimedia tools are an effective and promising tool (instrument) of education, which provides the teacher with a larger array of information than a traditional source of information; using not only text, graphics, schemes, but also sound, animations, video, etc. in a visual and harmonious way; provides an opportunity to select types of information in a sequence in accordance with the level of reception (perception) and logical learning of learners.

The main problems and disadvantages of using multimedia tools in education. There are also some common disadvantages of using multimedia in education. They include the division of attention, complications in creating materials, more time requirements, problems in setting up and using software and hardware, difficulties in the process of reading information from a computer screen, and other aspects.

Divided attention. The use of complex methods of presenting information in most cases can distract the attention of learners from the main topic being studied due to various inconsistencies. A large amount of information presented in multimedia tools, various links, etc., can distract the student during the lesson.

Difficulties in creating educational materials. Creating audio, video, graphic and other elements of multimedia is much more complicated than creating materials in the form of traditional text. More demand for time. Using multimedia as a learner requires a little more time than creating multimedia materials independently. In particular, it takes a lot of time and attention to create multimedia learning tools. Problems arising in the configuration and use of software and hardware. To ensure the effective use of multimedia educational tools, software and hardware must be configured to the required level. In this case, the process of providing multimedia educational materials requires higher quality and wider capabilities than simple means of editing and displaying texts. Difficulties in the process of reading information from a computer screen. Reading information from a computer screen is more inconvenient than reading information printed on paper. It is somewhat convenient to read large volumes of text information that require full reading, as well as newspapers, books and magazines in the printed version. In most cases, multimedia tools provide a data search tool to find the necessary information and print it on paper.

Conclusion:

Nowadays, everyone has a need to constantly use multimedia in their work. Multimedia tools are an integral part of modern information and communication technologies and have become a part of our life. The use of multimedia technologies in the educational process serves to increase the quality of education and the learning efficiency of the learner. Multimedia technologies make it possible to model macro- and microcosm processes and visualize them, record unforgettable moments, prepare entertainment materials, and create a basis for people's recreation and leisure.

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